

Short Article

Oxido-nitrosative stress and antioxidants in asthma

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Asthma is a pulmonary disease in which airways narrow and swell and produce excessive mucus, which impacts the breathing of an individual. Asthma affects over 15 million individuals in the United States. Asthma is characterized by systemic and chronic inflammation and oxidative stress of the lungs. Oxidative stress plays a critical role in the progression of several diseases including asthma. The inhaled oxidants, pollutants, allergens or antigens, as well as elevated amounts of intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS), released from inflammatory cells induced oxido-nitrosative stress. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) comprises superoxide anion (O_2^-) and the hydroxyl radical (OH) whereas Reactive nitrogen species (RNS) comprises nitric oxide (NO) and its derivatives peroxynitrite, ($ONOO^-$) that are unstable molecules with unpaired electrons (1, 2). These molecules induce oxidation of macromolecules such as proteins, DNA, and lipids and cause tissue injury and also induce a variety of cellular responses, via generation of secondary metabolic reactive species (3). Oxido-nitrosative stress in asthma occurs via free radical generation in two types.

One is by environmental exposures to allergens, antigens or air pollutants that range from cigarette smoke, oxidant gases, or airborne particulate matter and pollen or house dust mites. On the other hand due to immune cell infiltration myeloperoxidase (MPO) release from neutrophils, monocytes and macrophages, eosinophil peroxidase (EPO) from eosinophils, and NADPH oxidase, xanthine oxidase release due to the oxido-metabolic process from peroxisomes, endoplasmic reticulum, and mitochondrial stress-induced free radicals. The molecular mechanism of oxidative stress arises with the generation of various ROS molecules that results in NADPH oxidase-induced release of superoxide radical ($O_2^{\cdot-}$), by macrophages and eosinophils that interact with NO and forms peroxynitrite ($ONOO^-$). The $O_2^{\cdot-}$, also converts to hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) by superoxide dismutase (SOD) and produce hydroxide radical ($\cdot OH$) in the presence of Fe^{2+} via Fenton reaction and oxidize Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} . This conversion generates $\cdot OH$ direct from O_2^- and regenerates Fe^{2+} . The MPO

Figure1. Oxido-nitrosative stress in asthma. Extrinsic environmental factors such as allergens or antigens and intrinsic cellular factors such as NADPH oxidase, Xanthine oxidase, myeloperoxidase, peroxidases due to peroxisomes, endoplasmic reticulum, mitochondria stress induce immune responses that generate free radicals which form oxido-nitrosative stress and induce macromolecules such as DNA, lipid and protein damage.

catalyze hypochlorous acid (HOCl) and hypobromous acid (HOBr) from H₂O₂ in the presence of chloride (Cl⁻) and bromide (Br⁻) ions (4). Thus the free radical-mediated ROS generation induces cell signaling in pulmonary inflammation and asthma and alters cellular metabolism and function and exuberate immunological functions (Fig.1.). The airway inflammation in asthma induces edema, epithelial cell damage and infiltration of inflammatory cells such as mast cells, eosinophils, lymphocytes, monocytes, macrophages, and neutrophils in airways. The oxido-nitrosative stress and inflammation in lungs are observed with goblet cell hyperplasia, fibrosis, epithelial to mesenchymal transition and myofibroblast generation with airway wall remodeli-

ng. Inflammatory infiltrate increase is directly correlated with DNA damage, and increase in lipid peroxidation and 3-nitrotyrosine (3-NT) in atopic asthmatic patients along with IL8 and IL17 levels and eosinophils, neutrophils, and serum IgE levels (5). Antioxidant enzymes such as SOD, catalase, glutathione, glutathione peroxidase (GPx), glutathione reductase (GR) play a pivotal role in the balance of free radicals and reduce asthma and its associated allergy and inflammation (6). Antioxidants play a pivotal role in amelioration of asthmatic symptoms and disease progression and encounter the free radicals and defend the immune systems and regulate the cytokine release. Several pharmacological compounds

and drugs are proven as beneficial in the control of asthmatic symptoms and disease progression (7, 8). Th1/Th2/Th17 cytokines mediated immunological imbalance is observed in asthma and its associated oxidative stress, which further imbalance cytokine release and aggravate host immune responses in asthma patients. The antioxidant compounds melatonin and esculetin were shown to reduce Th2/Th17 cytokine-mediated asthmatic responses in murine models (9, 10). Low intake of dietary antioxidants is associated with atopic asthma and dietary antioxidants rich in fruits, vegetables, and antioxidant vitamins like Vitamin E and C and minerals such as magnesium is found to be beneficial in atopic asthmatic patients and in vulnerable population which is under calorie restriction due to socio-economic problems (11).

However, furthermore, research is necessary to better understand the oxido-nitrosative stress in asthma and its associated inflammation and allergic symptoms and the choice of antioxidants with regard to individual and environmental factors. In addition, further well-designed research and clinical trials will clarify the clinical value and significance of antioxidant therapy in the treatment of asthma and disease progression.

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